

DIAGNOSIS OF PATIENTS WITH DISTAL FORM OF HYPOSPADIA

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Relevance. Hypospadias is one of the most common congenital malformations of the male genitourinary system. This condition is characterized by the external opening of the urethra being located on the ventral surface of the penis, lower than its anatomically correct position at the other end.

The classic triad of signs includes: malposition of the meatus, ventral curvature of the penis (chorda), and abnormal development of the skin on the tip of the penis in the form of a dorsal "cap".

A modern approach to the diagnosis of distal forms of hypospadias requires a complex and systematic examination of patients in order to accurately assess the anatomical features of the defect, determine the optimal surgical tactics and predict the treatment results.

Distal hypospadias, although milder than proximal forms, is a significant medical and social problem. It causes urinary incontinence, cosmetic defects, and can affect sexual function, and therefore requires surgical treatment. Modern methods allow for one-stage correction in children under 12 months with good results, but the incidence of complications reaches 10-15%. The increasing prevalence of the disease and the need to improve surgical methods and long-term outcomes determine the relevance of a comprehensive study of distal hypospadias. This study systematizes current knowledge on the surgical treatment of distal forms of hypospadias, analyzes factors affecting outcomes, and identifies promising directions in pediatric urology.

The aim of the study - is to increase the effectiveness of treatment based on early diagnosis of patients with distal forms of hypospadias.

Material and methods. In this study, based on the experience of treating 191 patients, a standardized diagnostic algorithm was developed and scientifically justified, providing an individual approach to each clinical case.

Results and their discussion. This developed complex diagnostic algorithm is based on the principles of evidence-based medicine and includes successive stages with clear criteria for moving from one stage of examination to another.

Primary (anamnesis) diagnostic stage. At the first stage, special attention was paid to a thorough history taking. This included collecting information on family history, pregnancy and childbirth, and functional urinary disorders. Family

history can reveal a predisposition to hereditary anomalies of the development of the genitourinary system, which may occur in 7-14% of patients with hypospadias.

Clinical examination stage. In the second stage, the patient undergoes a standardized physical examination in a specially equipped room with sufficient lighting. The examination is carried out with the patient lying on his back, with an assessment of general physical development and a detailed analysis of the condition of the external genitalia.

Instrumental diagnostic methods. In our clinical practice, instrumental diagnostic methods were used differentially depending on clinical indications and the age of patients.

Ultrasound examination was performed in all patients. This examination included the assessment of the state of the kidneys and bladder, the anatomical structure of the urinary organs, as well as the determination of the amount of residual urine in children over 4 years of age.

Uroflowmetry was performed on patients over 4 years of age who could urinate independently. This method allows for an objective evaluation of disorders in the urodynamics of the urinary tract.

Additional examination methods were used according to indications: in case of suspected upper urinary tract anomalies - excretory urography; in case of urination disorders - micturition cystourethrography; in case of suspected sexual development disorders - karyotyping.

Conclusion. Indications for surgical treatment were determined comprehensively, taking into account the anatomical characteristics of the defect, functional disorders and psychosocial factors.

References:

1. Зиезода С.С., Ходжамурадов Г.М., Ризоев Х.Х., Шарипова М.Б. Метод местной пластики у пациентов при дистальных формах гипоспадии // Евразийский научно-медицинский журнал "Сино". – 2023. – Т.4, №2. – Стр.12-18.
2. Ибрагимов К.Н., Ахмедов Ю.М. Морфологическое исследование тканей при гипоспадии у детей // Здоровоохранение Таджикистана. – 2024. – №3. – Стр.112-113.
3. Каганцов И.М. Хирургическая коррекция гипоспадии у детей: дисс. канд. мед. наук. Ростов-на-Дону, 2015. 273 с.
4. Donaire A.E., Mendez M.D. Hypospadias. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2023 Jan. Last Update: July 31, 2023. PMID: 29489253.

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5. Effendi R., Situmorang G.R., Wahyudi I., Rodjani A. et al. Adult Sexual Function Following Hypospadias Repair in Childhood: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis of Long-term Patient Outcomes. *Urology*. 2025 May 16:S0090-4295(25)00471-6. doi: 10.1016/j.urology.2025.05.015.
6. European Association of Urology. EAU Guidelines on Paediatric Urology. – 2024. – URL: <https://uroweb.org/guidelines>

